
Plan Overview

A Data Management Plan created using DMPonline

Title: Study of Unconventional T cells

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Funder: Cancer Research UK (CRUK)

Template: Standard CRUK Template

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Project abstract:

There are subpopulations of T cells considered as 'unconventional' T cells, in part because they can recognize lipids, small-molecule metabolites and specially modified peptides. Some of the recent results proved the significance of these innate lymphoid cells in solid tumors and haematological malignancies, however, their exact contribution to the anti-tumor activity remains controversial. Our aim is to investigate the presence and function of these unconventional cells (e.g. gamma-delta T cells, mucosal associated T cells, invariant NK cells) and their relationship to other lymphocyte populations in patients with B cell chronic lymphocytic leukaemia and multiple myeloma. We also would like to characterize the effect of different therapies on these populations.

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Study of Unconventional T cells

Data description

The graphical representation from the statistical calculation would be expected from the project. 200 samples would be analysed and around 10 figures are expected.

The FCS file take around 3 GB of the data from all those samples and around 1 GB are expected from the spreadsheet and graphpad analysis file altogether.

The internal storage of the department server along with back up schedule would be enough to store and manage all the data.

Data standards

FCS format is standard to collect information from flow cytometry data. They will be collected and saved by the initial name of the donor samples and the spread sheet would be maintained for the demographic details of the data collected from individuals along with numerical values.

If any case of repeated samples initial name of the donor with sample 1 and 2 would be indicated in FCS file as well as in the spreadsheet.

Metadata and documentation

A read me file would be created in the folder where every description of the data would be mentioned. The metadata would include the filenames based on dates and versions such as v1, v1.1 v2 if needed. There will be an separate folders for each of different experiments and the experiment which are similar would be saved in same folder named as different dates and versions if needed.

Data sharing

The data would be shared anonymously with encryption through the emails to the collaborators. Data will not be shared by any physical drive with the exception of data protection with three different places as a backup.

Once the prospective manuscript are published, then the data would be released and make it public after 6 months of publication.

The data contain donor confidential, demographic, hematological, health information which could not be released without anonymous

Preservation Plan

Upon finishing the project, all the anonymised data would be uploaded to the open access servers such as zenodo for the availability. also the same data would be stored at University data repository for the future followup studies